

Friginal Eric & Hardy, Jack A. (2014). *Corpus-based sociolinguistics: A guide for students*. New York and London: Routledge

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Book review

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ABSTRACT

EN This review highlights the content of *Corpus-Based Sociolinguistics: A Guide for Students* by Eric Friginal and Jack A. Hardy, which maps out a clear and systematic path for corpus applications in sociolinguistics.

Key words: CORPORA, CORPUS TOOLS, LANGUAGE VARIATION AND CHANGE, VARIATION IN DISCOURSE.

ES La presente reseña realiza un repaso por lo más destacado de *Corpus-Based Sociolinguistics: A guide for Students*, obra escrita por Eric Friginal y Jack A. Hardy que pretende ofrecer al lector pautas claras y sistemáticas en la aplicación de corpus a la sociolingüística

Palabras clave: CORPUS, HERRAMIENTAS DE CORPUS, VARACIÓN LINGÜÍSTICA Y CAMBIO LINGÜÍSTICO, VARACIÓN EN EL DISCURSO.

IT L'obiettivo dell'articolo è mettere in rilievo i punti principali di *Corpus-Based Sociolinguistics: A guide for Students*, di Eric Friginal e Jack A. Hardy, che delinea un percorso chiaro e sistematico per l'applicazione del corpus in sociolinguistica.

Parole chiave: CORPORA, STRUMENTI DEL CORPUS, VARIAZIONE E CAMBIAMENTO LINGUISTICO, VARIAZIONE DEL DISCORSO.

Corpus-Based Sociolinguistics: A Guide for Students by Eric Friginal and Jack A. Hardy is a 312-page reference book which maps out a clear and systematic path for corpus applications in sociolinguistics. The book is divided into three sections, which introduce basic concepts related to corpus-based sociolinguistics, survey the main studies of the discipline, and offer ideas on how to conduct corpus-based sociolinguistic studies, respectively.

Section A, *Introduction to Corpus-Based Sociolinguistics*, is made up of five parts. The first focuses on sociolinguistic investigations of variation, and after defining the concept of variation and introducing the linguistic and societal variables in sociolinguistics, overviews the main applications, investigations, and approaches in corpus-based sociolinguistics. The second, third, and fourth parts offer an in-depth account of corpus linguistics by defining the discipline and its historical development and describing the main types of corpora, the common linguistic constructs investigated using corpora, and the software tools and corpus-based techniques which can be applied to sociolinguistic analyses. In these parts, the authors also take into account important issues in corpus design and representativeness. Finally, the fifth part considers the modern expansion of corpus work, as well as its limitations and likely future directions.

Section B, *Survey of Corpus-Based Sociolinguistic Studies*, offers concise but detailed information about studies in corpus-based sociolinguistic research. In the six parts making up this section, readers will find a kaleidoscopic compendium of corpora and of studies in language variation related to regional dialectology, gender, sexuality, age, politeness, stance, workplace discourse, diachronic change, and social media and web registers, among others.

Section C, *Conducting Corpus-Based Sociolinguistic Studies*, is the most practical of the sections. Although it is worth highlighting that the whole book is characterized by a constant and valuable zooming in

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and out from theory to practice and vice versa, Section C provides the most practical advice on how to conceive and develop corpora to conduct sociolinguistic research. In the first of the four parts of the section, the authors provide guidelines on not only how to collect and organize a corpus, but also on what to do before collecting one. The remaining parts amply illustrate issues such as multidimensional analysis of linguistic variation, diachronic research, and applications, such as keyword analysis, the Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count, and using POS-tagged data in sociolinguistic research.

The volume offers more than it promises: It not only succeeds in providing an up-to-date account of using corpora in sociolinguistic research, but it also succeeds in providing reflective breaks, text samples, sample research questions, case studies, further readings, interviews, trivia, vignettes, discussion questions, activities and applications, which are stimulating resources both for students and non-students. Although it is primarily intended as a guide to corpus-based sociolinguistics in upper-level undergraduate and graduate courses, the book is also a must read for professional researchers who are interested in a current, wide-ranging overview of corpus-based sociolinguistic research. The authors successfully synthesize a representative body of studies, concepts, and tools in sociolinguistic research, as they weave their way through a variety of topics, devices, and perspectives.

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